

Original Article

Medical education as a necessitate for field force.

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Abstract

Caregivers are important escort in the healing journey of any patient. Our country in last decades excel so much in terms of offering training programmes for nurses and midwives to bridge the gap between the therapeutic interventions and knowledge of these working individuals. We have done a survey on 182 nurses both male and female working in specifically small towns and trust hospitals. They were interviewed about their skills and the duties allocated to them. With reference to the patient care and conditions they were inquired about the medical background and awareness of the sufferer's ailment. We have found nearly disappointing results as almost 71% of these workers were ignorant of the fact that they lack basic knowledge of related medical conditions of concerned patients. Rest of the data also gave the evidence for a huge breach among the awareness, education and realistic approach in this selected workforce. We suggest that caregivers must be aware of indications and have strong medical foundation of the concerned departments where they are serving. We propose the medical education and clinical workshops for this set of serving individuals at ground levels along with the technical fine tuning with the help of case studies and practice. We recommend to improve this field force especially who are serving the majorities and in rural areas.

Keywords

Care givers, Health care, Medical Education, Nurses, Midwives

Introduction

Health care is an exciting field but as the same time it is also challenging due to the concerns that surrounds it. The responsibilities of health care providers are consistently changing and expanding. As alternative and complementary health care practices growing in popularity in public challenges the health care providers especially nurses to understand those miscellaneous approaches that helps them in effective working with the patients. (Ellis, 2004) At present nursing is defined as practicing and inquiring field and of course there must be an ultimate goal of health commitment for each and every member of society-goal that directs the actions of all health care providers in spite of the fact that there are no clear or widely accepted conception of ideas of scientific investigation programs for nursing.

The status of this discipline is strictly linked to length and consistency of the education required for the entrance into practice (Johnson,1968 & Joel, 2002). Presently nursing is involved in the hurting experiencing system as it was developed to fulfill professional prestige while at the same time health care delivery system demands nurses with increased knowledge, counseling and health education, as well instructed professional is a necessary requirement for

strong and supportive system. Various studies investigates and suggests that efforts to select and maintain baccalaureate-prepared nurses in bedside care and investments in advance education for nurses may lead to extensive progression in quality of care (Aiken, 2003).

Methodology

This a retrospective study in which the data was gathered through self-questionnaire for the selected variables from territory care Hospital of Karachi and the data was analyzing by using SPSS software. Information relating to the practices, duties, patient care and basic knowledge of related medical conditions were interviewed from male and female nurses.

Results

We have found nearly disappointing results as almost 71% of these workers were ignorant of the fact that they lack basic knowledge of related medical conditions of concerned patients while only 29% of Health providers have the required medical knowledge. Rest of the data also gave the evidence for a huge breach among the awareness, education and realistic approach in this selected workforce

Figure 1

Discussion

The growing size complexity and cost of health facilities in a growing population is a matter of universal concern. This matter of raising awareness is not new as there were numerous studies that are being conducted focusing on the health provider's duties as patient care, medical care or hospital care. This paper see the insights progress in the level of nursing knowledge about basic aspects of related medical conditions of concerned patients and why nurses knowledge in this extent is important (McCaffrey, 1997) and what should nurses be familiar with to provide high quality of care for patient. Nurses are more likely to spend most of their time with patients than any other health care provider. It's the nurse who tends to be in a position to evaluate the usefulness of the patient's illness management plan and in initiation of required changes. Thus, there are numerous nursing activities, for which considerable level of awareness and knowledge is essential. Firstly documented under treatment was in 1970s which was assumed to be as a result of lack of education among health-care professionals (Charap, 1978 & Marks 1973). Therefore, various efforts were increasingly prepared over the next decades to re-instruct health-care providers, resulting in the development and extensive spreading of guidelines for clinical practices (AHCPR, 1992). Learning efforts engaging nurses seems to have contributed towards improving and raising their awareness and knowledge levels. Altogether, it appears that the longer nurses are accessing the correct information, the more improved and increased their knowledge level develops (American Pain Society, 1992). While knowledge alone itself is not enough to

assure advancement in patient care, it is the first step. But in the absenteeism of accurate information, patient care is not likely to improve. Secondly, to make the most of the impact of educational ways, the content of both continuing education offerings as well as basic nursing programs must be examined critically for applicability and accurateness. Nurses should be encouraged to increase their knowledge and be held responsible for assuming their everyday jobs and accountabilities.

Conclusion

The changed scope of nursing practice, the intellectual growth of the discipline, and the increased demands of the service environment bring an ethical obligation to consider complementary changes in nursing education, to revisit the "entry" issue.

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Ethical clearance

Ethical approval was obtained from Institution Review Board of AEIRC.

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Conflict of Interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Ellis, J. R., & Hartley, C. L. (2004). *Nursing in today's world: trends, issues & management*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Johnson, D. E. (1968). One conceptual model of nursing. *Vanderbilt University, Nashville, TN*.
- Joel, L. (2002). Education for entry into nursing practice: Revisited for the 21st century. *Online journal of issues in nursing*, 7(2), 4.
- Aiken, L. H., Clarke, S. P., Cheung, R. B., Sloane, D. M., & Silber, J. H. (2003). Educational levels of hospital nurses and surgical patient mortality. *Jama*, 290(12), 1617-1623.
- McCaffrey, M., & Ferrell, B. R. (1997). Nurses' knowledge of pain assessment and management: How much progress have we made?. *Journal of pain and symptom management*, 14(3), 175-188.
- Charap AD. The knowledge, attitudes, and experience of medical personnel treating pain in the terminally ill. *Mt Sinai J Med* 1978;45:561-580.
- Marks RM, Sachar EJ. Undertreatment of medical inpatients with narcotic analgesics. *Ann Intern Med* 1973;78:173-181.
- Agency for Health Care Policy and Research. Acute pain management in adults: operative procedures. Quick reference guide for clinicians. Agency for Health Care Policy and Research (AHCPR) publication no. 92-0019. Rockville, MD: AHCPR, 1992.
- American Pain Society. Principles of analgesic use in the treatment of acute pain and cancer pain, 3rd ed. Skokie, IL: American Pain Society, 1992.
- McCaffery M, Ferrell BR. Nurses' knowledge about cancer pain: a survey of five countries. *J Pain Symptom Manage* 1995; 10:356-369.